

Fluctuation Theory and Microscopic Reversibility vis-a-vis Higher Order Symmetries[†]

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Attempts have been made for obtaining higher order symmetries on the basis of the fluctuation theory and the theory of microscopic reversibility. The results obtained are in conformity with those obtained from steady state thermodynamic considerations.

THE basic foundation of the Onsager's reciprocity relation^{1,2}, which has, by now, very much stood the test³⁻⁹ of time and is now accepted as an axiom is the fluctuation theory. The Li's higher order symmetries¹⁰⁻¹¹ which may be regarded as a logical extension or a mathematical corollary of the first order symmetry, still very much lie on the test board for a verdict on its merit, and only the future can give an assessment on this. An attempt to realize these higher order symmetries¹⁰⁻¹⁸ in the perspective of the fluctuation theory¹⁹⁻²² and the theory of microscopic reversibility²³⁻²⁵ may be a useful contribution in this regard. The present communication is one such attempt in the said direction.

We consider an adiabatically insulated system defined or characterized by n degrees of advancement $\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3 \dots \xi_n$, where n may become eventually infinite. The deviations of the ξ_i from their equilibrium value ξ_i^e , is denoted by α_i so that

$$\alpha_i = (\xi_i - \xi_i^e) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

As state variables we might think of local temperature, pressure, densities and the like for the description of the thermodynamical state of the system. The stress lies, in particular, on the point that in every microscopic theory one may choose continually varying parameters such as above, since in such cases only the number of variables become infinite. In the present discussion, however, we would like to advance our argument by using the degree of advancement from the equilibrium value as parameters.

The entropy change in any system is described by the sum total of the product of the fluxes, J_i , and their conjugate forces, X_i , operative in the system. If we choose A/T as a force, where A is the affinity of a chemical reaction at the temperature T of the system in Kelvin scale, then in present

case of continuous range of advancement from equilibrium value, as the parameters, we obtain the entropy as given under

$$\Delta_i S = \int_{\xi^e}^{\xi} diS = \int_{\xi^e}^{\xi} \frac{A}{T} d\xi \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where $d\xi$ represents an infinitesimal change between the two subsequent advancements, which acts as a flux. Expressing A in the Taylor type expansion form, and remembering that $A(\xi^e)$ i.e., equilibrium affinity of a chemical reaction, is zero²⁶, we rewrite equation (2) through equation (3) as given in equation (4)

$$A = \left(\frac{\delta A}{\delta \xi} \right)_0 \alpha + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{\delta^2 A}{\delta \xi^2} \right)_0 \alpha^2 + \dots \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_i S &= \int \left(\frac{A}{T} \right) d\xi \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \int \left[\left(\frac{\delta A}{\delta \xi} \right)_0 \alpha + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{\delta^2 A}{\delta \xi^2} \right)_0 \alpha^2 + \dots \right] d\xi \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{\delta A}{\delta \xi} \right)_0 \frac{\alpha^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2!} \frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{\delta^2 A}{\delta \xi^2} \right)_0 \frac{\alpha^3}{3} \\ &\quad + \dots \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

$\Delta_i S$, in equation (4) is the total entropy production occurring in the system which is thus obtained as the sum of the separate entropy contributions due to the various orders of deviations from equilibrium values of the different parameters which represent the various orders of forces operative in the system. These may be assumed to represent correspondingly the entropy contributions due to the first, the second and the third order forces etc., operating in the system and may be represented as

$$\Delta_i S = \Delta_i S' + \Delta_i S'' + \Delta_i S''' + \dots \quad (5)$$

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Differentiation of equation (4) with respect to α gives

$$\frac{\delta \Delta_i S}{\delta \alpha} = \frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{\delta A}{\delta \xi} \right)_0 \alpha + \frac{1}{T} \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{\delta^2 A}{\delta \xi^2} \right)_0 \alpha^2 + \dots \quad (6)$$

which in the event of simultaneous fluctuations of various parameters of the system, takes a more general and comprehensive form as given under

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_i S = & \frac{1}{T} \frac{1}{2!} \sum_{ij} \left(\frac{\delta A_i}{\delta \xi_j} \right)_0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \\ & + \frac{1}{T} \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{ijk} \left(\frac{\delta^2 A_i}{\delta \xi_j \delta \xi_k} \right)_0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \alpha_k + \dots \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

where i, j, k etc may each assume the values, 1,2,3,n. Equation (7) on differentiation with respect to α_i gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta \Delta_i S}{\delta \alpha_i} = & \frac{1}{T} \sum_j \left(\frac{\delta A_i}{\delta \xi_j} \right)_0 \alpha_j \\ & + \frac{1}{T} \frac{1}{2!} \sum_{jk} \left(\frac{\delta^2 A_i}{\delta \xi_j \delta \xi_k} \right)_0 \alpha_j \alpha_k \dots \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Identifying $\frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{\delta A}{\delta \xi_j} \right)_0$ with $-g_{ij}$ and

$\frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{\delta^2 A_i}{\delta \xi_j \delta \xi_k} \right)_0$ with $-g_{ijk}$ and so on equation (8) is written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta \Delta_i S}{\delta \alpha_i} = & - \sum_j g_{ij} \alpha_j \alpha_k \\ & - \frac{1}{2!} \sum_{jk} g_{ijk} \alpha_i \alpha_k \dots \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

Equation (5) on similar differentiation yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta \Delta_i S}{\delta \alpha_i} = & \frac{\delta \Delta_i S'}{\delta \alpha_i} + \frac{\delta \Delta_i S''}{\delta \alpha_i} + \frac{\delta \Delta_i S'''}{\delta \alpha_i} + \dots \\ = & X_i + X''_i + X'''_i + \dots \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

where each of the terms in the r.h.s. of equation (10) is defined as the first, the second and the third order force etc and is correspondingly represented as $X'_i + X''_i + X'''_i \dots$ etc.

Equation (9) and (10) together give the following equalities

$$X'_i = \frac{\delta \Delta_i S'}{\delta \alpha_i} = - \sum_j g_{ij} \alpha_j$$

$$X''_i = \frac{\delta \Delta_i S''}{\delta \alpha_i} = - \frac{1}{2!} \sum_{jk} g_{ijk} \alpha_j \alpha_k$$

$$X'''_i = \frac{\delta \Delta_i S'''}{\delta \alpha_i} = - \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{jkl} g_{ijkl} \alpha_j \alpha_k \alpha_l$$

and so on ... (11)

Einstein's fluctuation theory¹⁹⁻²¹ states that the probability of finding a state, in which the values of the α_i lie between α_i and $d\alpha_i$, is given^{8,9} by

$$\begin{aligned} P d\alpha_1 d\alpha_2 \dots d\alpha_n = & \frac{e^{\Delta_i S/k} d\alpha_1 d\alpha_2 \dots d\alpha_n}{\int \dots \int e^{\Delta_i S/k} d\alpha_1 d\alpha_2 \dots d\alpha_n} \dots (12) \end{aligned}$$

where the denominator on the right hand ensures normalisation of P over the complete configurational space to unity, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \int \dots \int e^{\Delta_i S/k} d\alpha_1 d\alpha_2 \dots d\alpha_n \\ = \int \dots \int P d\alpha_1 d\alpha_2 \dots d\alpha_n = 1 \dots \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

where k in the above equations symbolises Boltzmann's constant.

Hence, from equations (12) and (5) we have,

$$\begin{aligned} P = & e^{\Delta_i S/k} \\ = & e^{\Delta_i S'/k + \Delta_i S''/k + \Delta_i S'''/k + \dots} \\ = & e^{\Delta_i S'/k} \cdot e^{\Delta_i S''/k} \cdot e^{\Delta_i S'''/k} \dots \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

or

$$P = P' \cdot P'' \cdot P''' \dots \dots \quad (15)$$

where P is the total probability and P', P'' and P''' etc are the probabilities correspondingly related to $\Delta_i S'$, $\Delta_i S''$ and $\Delta_i S'''$ etc, which in turn are respectively connected with the first, the second and the third order forces etc. From equations (10), (14) and (15) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} X'_i + X''_i + X'''_i + \dots = & \frac{\delta \Delta_i S'}{\delta \alpha_i} + \frac{\delta \Delta_i S''}{\delta \alpha_i} + \\ & \frac{\delta \Delta_i S'''}{\delta \alpha_i} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{K \delta \log P'''}{\delta \alpha_i} + \frac{K \delta \log P''}{\delta \alpha_i} + \frac{K \delta \log P'}{\delta \alpha_i} + \dots (16)$$

Multiplication of the first, the second and the

$$\left[K \int \dots \int d\alpha_1 \dots d\alpha_{i-1} d\alpha_{i+1} \dots d\alpha_n \left\{ \left[\alpha_k \cdot P''_2 \right]_{-\infty}^{+\infty} - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P''_2 \frac{\delta \alpha_k}{\delta \alpha_i} d\alpha_i \right\} \right] \dots (24)$$

with the conditions that

P''_1 is zero for $\alpha_i = \pm \infty$ and

P''_2 is zero for $\alpha_k = \pm \infty$
expression (24) reduces to

$$\left[-K \int \dots \int d\alpha_1 \dots d\alpha_{i-1} \dots d\alpha_{i+1} \dots d\alpha_n \int P''_1 \frac{\delta \alpha_j}{\delta \alpha_i} d\alpha_i \right] \left[-K \int \dots \int d\alpha_1 \dots d\alpha_{i-1} \dots d\alpha_{i+1} \dots d\alpha_n \int P''_2 \frac{\delta \alpha_k}{\delta \alpha_i} d\alpha_i \right] \dots (25)$$

Since α_i, α_j and α_k are independent variables, hence,

$$\frac{\delta \alpha_j}{\delta \alpha_i} = 1 \text{ or } \delta_{ij} = 1 \text{ when } \alpha_i = \alpha_j \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{\delta \alpha_j}{\delta \alpha_i} = 0 \text{ or } \delta_{ij} = 0 \text{ when } \alpha_i \neq \alpha_j$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker symbol⁹.

Similarly,

$$\frac{\delta \alpha_k}{\delta \alpha_i} = 1 \text{ or } \delta_{ik} = 1 \text{ when } \alpha_i = \alpha_k \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{\delta \alpha_k}{\delta \alpha_i} = 0 \text{ or } \delta_{ik} = 0 \text{ when } \alpha_i \neq \alpha_k$$

Expression (25) again reduces to

$$\left[-K \int \dots \int d\alpha_1 \dots d\alpha_{i-1} \dots d\alpha_{i+1} \dots d\alpha_n \int P''_1 \delta_{ij} d\alpha_i \right] \left[-K \int \dots \int d\alpha_1 \dots d\alpha_{i-1} \dots d\alpha_{i+1} \dots d\alpha_n \int P''_2 \delta_{ik} d\alpha_i \right] \dots (26)$$

using the normalisation condition, expression (26) gives,

$$\left[-K \cdot \delta_{ij} \right] \left[-K \cdot \delta_{ik} \right] = K^2 \cdot \delta_{ij} \delta_{ik} \dots (27)$$

The principle of microscopic reversibility^{8,9,23-25} states that the correlation in an "aged" system among the values of α_h, α_i at a time instant t and a value of α_j a time τ later is the same as the correlation between $\alpha_h(t), \alpha_i(t)$ and a value of α_j a time τ

earlier^{8,9}. The same fact may also be expressed in an alternative manner such as

$$\overline{\alpha_h(t) \alpha_i(t) \alpha_j(t+\tau)} = \overline{\alpha_h(t) \alpha_i(t+\tau) \alpha_j(t)} \dots (28)$$

The averaging is performed by taking first, the fixed values of the parameters at the time t and then averaging the quantities belonging to the time $t+\tau$ followed by the application of the same consideration with all the parameters in question, and then finally averaging over all, which is expressed in the formula as

$$\overline{\alpha_h(t) \alpha_i(t) \overline{\alpha_j(t+\tau)}} \overline{\alpha_h(t)} \dots \alpha_n(t) = \overline{\alpha_h(t) \alpha_j(t) \overline{\alpha_i(t+\tau)}} \overline{\alpha_h(t)} \dots \alpha_n(t) \dots (29)$$

following the procedure of De Groot⁹, and subtracting the same quantity, $\alpha_h(t) \alpha_i(t) \alpha_j(t)$ from both members of equation(29) we obtain

$$\overline{\alpha_h(t) \alpha_i(t) \overline{\alpha_j(t+\tau)} - \alpha_j(t) \alpha_h(t)} \dots \alpha_n(t) = \overline{\alpha_h(t) \alpha_j(t) \overline{\alpha_i(t+\tau)} - \alpha_i(t) \alpha_h(t)} \dots \alpha_n(t) \dots (30)$$

we now co-relate the rate of decay as linear combination with the second order force (X''_k), [c. f. equation (10)] as follows

$$\frac{\overline{\alpha_i(t+\tau) - \alpha_i(t)}}{\tau} = \bar{\alpha} \cdot (\text{rate of decay}) \equiv J_i (\text{flux}) = \sum_{h,k=1}^n L_{ihk} X''_k \dots (31)$$

the l. h. s. of equation (31) denote the rate of decay of fluctuation and L_{ihk} in the r. h. s. is the second order phenomenological coefficient of the second order force of the type X''_k . In equation (31) the time interval τ is limited by the conditions⁹

$$\tau_0 < \tau < \tau_r$$

where τ_0 is the characteristic molecular time i.e., the time between two successive collisions of the molecules and τ_r is the regression time of a fluctuation i.e., at a time in which the deviation from equilibrium is appreciably reduced. On similar consideration we obtain

$$\frac{\overline{\alpha_j(t+\tau) - \alpha_j(t)}}{\tau} = \bar{\alpha}_j \equiv J_j = \sum_{h,k=1}^n L_{jhk} X''_k \dots (32)$$

On the basis of equations (31) and (32) one gets from equation (30) as

$$\overline{\alpha_j(t) \alpha_i(t) \alpha_h(t)} = \bar{\alpha}_j(t) \alpha_i(t) \alpha_h(t) \dots (33)$$

Putting the value of equations (31) and (32) in equation (33) we have

$$\sum_{h,k} L_{ihk} \overline{\alpha_j \alpha_h X_k''} = \sum_{h,k} L_{jhk} \overline{\alpha_i \alpha_h X_k''} \quad \dots \quad (34)$$

Equations (33) and (34) read with equation (27) give

$$\overline{\alpha_j \alpha_h X_k''} = K^2 [\delta_{kj} \delta_{kh}] \quad \dots \quad (35)$$

and

$$\overline{\alpha_i \alpha_h X_k''} = K^2 [\delta_{ki} \delta_{kh}] \quad \dots \quad (36)$$

Putting the value of equations (33) and (36) in equation (34) we obtain

$$K^2 \sum_{h,k} \left[\begin{matrix} \delta_{hj} \delta_{kh} \\ \delta_{ki} \delta_{kh} \end{matrix} \right] L_{thk} = K^2 \sum_{h,k} L_{jhk}$$

or

$$\sum_{h,k} [\delta_{kj} \delta_{kh}] L_{thk} = \sum_{h,k} [\delta_{ki} \delta_{kh}] L_{jhk} \quad \dots \quad (37)$$

Kronecker symbols δ_{kj} , δ_{kh} and δ_{ki} come out unity in the l.h.s. and r.h.s. of equation (37) when

$$\begin{aligned} K = j, \quad \delta_{kj} = \delta_{,,} = 1 \\ K = h, \quad \delta_{kh} = \delta_{,,} = 1 \\ K = i, \quad \delta_{ki} = \delta_{,,} = 1 \quad \dots \quad (38) \end{aligned}$$

Equation (37) is valid only for the conditions expressed in (38). Putting the condition of equation (38) in equation (37) we obtain the second order symmetries as given under

$$\sum L_{ihk} = \sum L_{jhk} \quad \dots \quad (39)$$

To exemplify the validity of the equality expressed above we consider first the l.h.s. of equation (39) with the condition given in the r.h.s. of equation (40). This yields

$$\sum L_{ihk} = \sum_{j=h=k} L_{ijj} \quad \dots \quad (40)$$

$$\sum L_{jhk} = \sum_{j=h, i=k} L_{jji} \quad \dots \quad (41)$$

whereby we obtain

$$\sum_{j=h=k} L_{ijj} = \sum_{j=h, i=k} L_{jji} \quad \dots \quad (42)$$

and similarly we also obtain,

$$\sum_{i=h, j=k} L_{ijj} = \sum_{i=h=k} L_{jji} \quad \dots \quad (43)$$

Likewise if we proceed with third term of the expression (18) and utilising the same procedure as adopted earlier we get

$$\overline{X_i \alpha_j \alpha_k \alpha_l} = K \int \dots \int \alpha_j \alpha_k \alpha_l \frac{\delta \log p''}{\delta \alpha_i}$$

$$p'' \cdot d\alpha_1 \cdot d\alpha_2 \dots \dots \dots d\alpha_n$$

Splitting X_i''' as the product of three fluctuating parameters i.e.,

$$X_i''' = X_{i_1}''' X_{i_2}''' X_{i_3}''' \quad \dots \quad (44)$$

and stepping on the footsteps of our previous arguments (c.f. equation 21-27) we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{X_i \alpha_j \alpha_k \alpha_l} &= \overline{X_{i_1}''' \alpha_j \alpha_k \alpha_l} \\ &= -K^3 [\delta_{ij} \delta_{ik} \delta_{il}] \quad \dots \quad (45) \end{aligned}$$

which finally gives,

$$\begin{aligned} -K^3 \sum_{hkl} [\delta_{kj} \delta_{kh} \delta_{kl}] L_{ihkl} \\ = -K^3 \sum_{hkl} [\delta_{ki} \delta_{kh} \delta_{kl}] L_{jhkl} \quad \dots \quad (46) \end{aligned}$$

and from this we obtain, the third order symmetries of the form,

$$\sum L_{ihkl} = \sum L_{jhkl} \quad \dots \quad (47)$$

The equality given in (47) may similarly be tested. This, with the condition mentioned under, gives the symmetries of the type

$$\sum_{j=k=l, i=h} L_{ijj} = \sum_{i=k=l, j=h} L_{jji} \quad \dots \quad (48)$$

$$\sum_{j=h=k, i=l} L_{ijj} = \sum_{j=h=k, i=l} L_{jji} \quad \dots \quad (49)$$

and

$$\sum_{\substack{i=j=k, \\ j=1}} L_{ijij} = \sum_{\substack{i=h=k=1}} L_{jiii} \quad \dots \quad (50)$$

From what have been discussed above it would be evidently clear that if we proceed with the force of fourth and fifth terms etc of equation (18) respectively with identical approach we would correspondingly observe the fourth and fifth order symmetries etc. as has been verified on kinetic considerations of the classical theories in some of the earlier communications^{1,4,16,27}, as a logical consequence.

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